

SYNTHESIS OF LOCAL ANAESTHETICS. PART IV.

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Some piperidino- and diethylamino-acetyl and propionyl amines have been prepared and their local anaesthetic properties studied.

Percaine, the hydrochloride of β -diethylaminoethylamide of 2-butoxyquinoline-4-carboxylic acid has potent local anaesthetic activity (*cf.* Jones, "Anaesthesia and Analgesia", 1930, 2 218; Keyes and McIellan *J. Amer. Med. Assoc.*, 1931, 96, 2086, Rosenstein, *Deutsch. Med. Wochenschr.*, 1929, 55, 2010, etc.). All these workers have found percaine to be one hundred times more effective on rabbit's cornea. Hoffer (*Klin. Woch.*, 1929, 8, 1249) finds that this drug is twelve times more effective than cocaine clinically. It is also stated to be twenty and ten times more powerful than novocaine and tutocaine respectively. It possesses a further advantage in that its solutions may be sterilised by boiling without loss of activity. On the other hand, it has a fairly high degree of toxicity (Freund, *Klin. Woch.* 1929, 8, 1444).

Apart from the clinical advantages of this drug there is a theoretical interest in that it has typical ester grouping in the molecule replaced by an amide grouping. It appeared of interest to us to synthesise simple amides and see if any local anaesthetic properties develop in such compounds. Nirvaine (4-dimethylaminoacetyl-2-carbomethoxy-phenol) is a local anaesthetic belonging to the amide class but the typical ester grouping of cocaine is present in the molecule.

We decided to synthesise simple amides of the general formula (I).

The substances where R = OMe, OEt etc., $n = 1$ or 2, $\text{R}_1 = \text{R}_2 = \text{Et}$ or NR_1R_2 replaced by piperidino, have been prepared and some compounds have been found to have some local anaesthetic action as determined by the rabbits' cornea method. The position of R in the nucleus with respect to the side-chain has also been varied and the results obtained have been recorded in the experimental sequel.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

ω -Piperidinoacetyl-*o*-phenetidine (I, R = OEt in *ortho* position, R_1, R_2 replaced by piperidine and $n = 1$),—To ω -chloroacetyl-*o*-phenetidine (m.p.

64°, cf. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1919, **41**, 1452) (2 g.) dissolved in dry benzene was added piperidine (2 c.c.) and the mixture refluxed for 4-5 hours on the steam-bath. After the precipitated solids were collected, the solvent was removed from the filtrate and the residual oil solidified on cooling. After washing with water, it was crystallised from hot dilute alcohol, m.p. 98°. (Found: N, 10.45. $C_{15}H_{22}O_2N_2$ requires N, 10.61 per cent). The *hydrochloride*, prepared with ethereal hydrogen chloride in dry ether solution, crystallised from a mixture of acetone and ether, m.p. 158°.

ω-Diethylaminoacetyl-o-phenetidine, prepared in an analogous manner with diethylamine in place of piperidine, was obtained as an oil which was converted into the *hydrochloride* which was then crystallised from a mixture of acetone and ether, m.p. 118°. (Found: N, 9.39; Cl, 12.5. $C_{14}H_{22}O_2N_2 \cdot HCl$ requires N, 9.7; Cl, 12.3 per cent).

β-Chloropropionyl-o-phenetidine.—To a cooled solution of *o*-phenetidine (5 g.) in glacial acetic acid (20 c.c.) mixed with a saturated solution of sodium acetate in water (20 c.c.), was added *β*-chloropropionyl chloride (4.6 g.). After standing for some time in the ice-bath, the mixture was poured into a large volume of water and the precipitate collected and crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 77°. (Found: N, 6.29. $C_{11}H_{14}O_2NCl$ requires N, 6.15 per cent).

β-Piperidinopropionyl-o-phenetidine (I, R = OEt in *ortho* position, $n = 2$, NR₁R₂ replaced by piperidine) was prepared from the foregoing compound in benzene solution by the method described before with a benzene solution of piperidine. The product was an oil; hence it was converted into the hydrochloride in the usual way and the hydrochloride crystallised from a mixture of acetone and ether, m.p. 102°. (Found: N, 8.7. $C_{16}H_{24}O_2N_2 \cdot HCl$ requires N, 8.9 per cent).

The related *β-diethylaminopropionyl-o-phenetidine hydrochloride*, prepared in an analogous way with diethylamine, had m.p. 126° after crystallisation from acetone and dry benzene. (Found: N, 9.62. $C_{15}H_{24}O_2N_2 \cdot HCl$ requires N, 9.33 per cent).

The *hydrochloride* of *ω-piperidinoacetyl-m-phenetidine*, prepared as described before, had m.p. 159°. (Found: N, 8.96. $C_{15}H_{22}O_2N_2 \cdot HCl$ requires N, 9.03 per cent).

ω-Diethylaminoacetyl-m-phenetidine hydrochloride had m.p. 180° after crystallisation from alcohol and acetone. (Found: N, 9.74. Calc. N, 10.2 per cent).

β-Chloropropionyl-m-phenetidine had m.p. 80-81°. *β-Piperidinopropionyl-m-phenetidine hydrochloride*, prepared in the usual way, had m.p.

244°. (Found: N, 10.9. Calc. N, 10.7 per cent.) and β -diethylamino-propionyl-*m*-phenetidine hydrochloride was an undistillable liquid.

ω -Piperidinoacetyl-*p*-phenetidine, prepared similarly to the related *ortho* compound, had m.p. 67° after crystallisation from petroleum ether. (Found: N, 10.7. Calc. N, 10.8 per cent).

ω -Diethylaminoacetylphenetidine hydrochloride had m.p. 154° after crystallisation from acetone and ether. (Found: N, 9.78. Calc. N, 9.77 per cent).

β -Chloropropionyl-*p*-phenetidine had m.p. 123° after crystallisation from alcohol. (Found: N, 6.4. Calc. N, 6.2 per cent). β -Piperidino-propionyl-*p*-phenetidine had m.p. 96° after crystallisation from petroleum ether. (Found: N, 10.16. Calc. N, 10.15 per cent). The hydrochloride had m.p. 199° after crystallisation from acetone-ether mixture.

The compounds enumerated in Table I were prepared in an analogous manner.

TABLE I.

	M.p.	Nitrogen	
		Found.	Calc.
1. Hydrochloride of β -diethylaminopropionyl- <i>p</i> -phenetidine (ex-acetone-dry ether)	119°	9.34%	9.31%
2. Hydrochloride of β -piperidinoacetyl- <i>o</i> -anisidine (ex-a mixture of acetone and benzene)	104°	9.84	9.84
3. Hydrochloride of diethylaminoacetyl- <i>o</i> -anisidine (ex-benzene)	171°	14.52	15.0
4. Hydrochloride of β -piperidinopropionyl- <i>o</i> -anisidine (ex-acetone-ether)	184°	9.94	9.7
5. Picrate of β -diethylaminopropionyl- <i>o</i> -anisidine (ex-benzene)	173°	14.74	14.82
6. Hydrochloride of β - <i>N</i> -piperidinoacetyl- <i>m</i> -anisidine (ex-acetone)	154°	9.84	9.96
7. Hydrochloride of diethylaminoacetyl- <i>m</i> -anisidine (ex-acetone)	144°	10.26	10.27
8. Chloropropionyl- <i>m</i> -anisidine (ex-petroleum ether)	92°	6.94	6.54
9. Hydrochloride of β - <i>N</i> -piperidinopropionyl- <i>m</i> -anisidine (ex-acetone)	194°	9.04	9.31
10. Hydrochloride of diethylaminopropionyl- <i>m</i> -anisidine (ex-benzene)	128°	14.66	14.61
11. Hydrochloride of ω - <i>N</i> -piperidinoacetyl- <i>p</i> -anisidine (ex-acetone)	160°	9.54	9.84
12. Hydrochloride of ω -diethylamino- <i>p</i> -anisidine (ex-alcohol-ether)	190°	10.07	10.29
13. β -Chloropropionyl- <i>p</i> -anisidine (ex-alcohol)	124°	6.7	6.6
14. β -Piperidinopropionyl- <i>p</i> -anisidine (ex-petroleum ether)	104°	10.5	10.6
15. Picrate of β -diethylaminopropionyl- <i>p</i> -anisidine (ex-methyl alcohol)	123°	14.82	14.9

The substances described in Table II were tested for their local anaesthetic efficiency on rabbits' cornea. Each substance was used in 2% solution and was compared with cocaine hydrochloride solution of the same strength. These results are the averages of ten experiments with each drug.

TABLE II.

(Values for cocaine hydrochloride are in parenthesis)

	Time for onset of anaesthesia, complete loss of reflex action.	Duration for which complete loss of reflex action lasted.
1. Hydrochloride of ω -piperidinoacetyl- <i>o</i> -phenetidine	1 min.	(1) 28 min. (37)
2. Hydrochloride of diethylaminoacetyl- <i>o</i> -phenetidine.	1	(1½) 18 „ (36)
3. Hydrochloride of β -piperidinopropionyl- <i>o</i> -phenetidine	5	(1) Partial anaesthesia lasting for 19 min. (36)
4. Hydrochloride of β -diethylamino-propionyl- <i>o</i> -phenetidine	1	(1) Partial anaesthesia lasting for 16 mins. (36)
5. Hydrochloride of ω -piperidinoacetyl- <i>m</i> -phenetidine	1	(1) 48 min. (35)
6. Hydrochloride of diethylaminoacetyl- <i>m</i> -phenetidine	1	(1½) 37 „ (36)
7. Hydrochloride of β -piperidinopropionyl <i>m</i> -phenetidine	1	(1) Incomplete anaesthesia lasting for 30 min. (36)
8. Hydrochloride of β -diethylamino-propionyl- <i>m</i> -phenetidine	1	(1½) Incomplete anaesthesia lasting for 25 min. (36)
9. Hydrochloride of ω -piperidinoacetyl- <i>p</i> -phenetidine	1	(1) 28 min. (36)
10. Hydrochloride of ω -diethylaminoacetyl- <i>p</i> -phenetidine	1	(1) 20 „ (35)
11. Hydrochloride of β -piperidinopropionyl- <i>p</i> -phenetidine	1	(1) Incomplete anaesthesia lasting for 18 min. (36)
12. Hydrochloride of β -diethylamino-propionyl- <i>p</i> -phenetidine	Never complete	(1) Incomplete anaesthesia (35)
13. Hydrochloride of ω -piperidinoacetyl- <i>o</i> -anisidine.	1 min.	(1½) 24 minutes (35)
14. Hydrochloride of diethylaminoacetyl- <i>o</i> -anisidine	1	(1) 15 „ (36)
15. Hydrochloride of β -piperidinopropionyl- <i>o</i> -anisidine	Never complete	(1) Incomplete anaesthesia (35)

TABLE II (contd.).

	Time for onset of anaesthesia, complete loss of reflex action.	Duration for which complete loss of reflex action lasted.
16. Hydrochloride of β -diethylaminopropionyl- <i>o</i> -anisidine	Never complete (1)	Never complete (37)
17. Hydrochloride of α -piperidinoacetyl- <i>m</i> -anisidine	5 min. (13)	30 minutes (35)
18. Hydrochloride of diethylaminoacetyl- <i>m</i> -anisidine	10 ,, (1)	24 ,, (35)
19. Hydrochloride of β -piperidinopropionyl- <i>m</i> -anisidine	Never complete (1)	Never complete (36)
20. Hydrochloride of β -diethylaminopropionyl- <i>m</i> -anisidine	Never complete (1)	Never complete (37)
21. Hydrochloride of α -piperidinoacetyl- <i>p</i> -anisidine	9 min. (1)	17 min. (36)
22. Hydrochloride of diethylaminoacetyl- <i>p</i> -anisidine	Never complete (1)	Never complete (36)
23. Hydrochloride of β -piperidinopropionyl- <i>p</i> -anisidine	,,	,,
24. Hydrochloride of β -diethylaminopropionyl- <i>p</i> -anisidine	,,	,,

From the above it would seem that the substances in the *meta* series have pronounced local anaesthetic action, the maximum effect being noticed in No. 5, whilst in the phenetidine series the compound No. 9 shows quite appreciable local anaesthetic activity. In both the compounds the side-chain has the piperidinoacetyl residue.

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